

Strategic Management Models & Indian Epics

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Abstract

A business strategy is the means by which it sets out to achieve its desired goal. A business strategy is concerned with major resource issues e.g. raising the finance to build a new factory or plant. Strategies are also concerned with deciding on what products to allocate major resources or ensure win in a given challenge. In this paper, we have discussed various strategic management models under the broad headings of generic strategies, competitive/red ocean strategies, monopoly/blue ocean strategies, sustainability/green ocean strategies, unethical/black ocean strategies and combined/white ocean strategies, their base in Indian epics like Ramayana and Mahabharata. The strategies used in Indian epics as examples for various modern strategies are analysed and their instances and implementations are discussed. Finally, Based on the analysis of all strategies, it is concluded that white ocean mixed strategy can be accepted as global strategy for the winners. Using PEST analysis, organizational global strategy can be correlated with White ocean mixed strategy as optimum strategy, an organization can be sustainable in global business.

Keywords : Strategic Management models, Strategy in Indian philosophy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Strategic management is the very important and very old area of business management even though the business strategy concepts have attracted organizations mainly in the last century. Strategic management concepts supported the organizations to ensure winning in their objectives based on long term planning and finding optimum solutions to their problems within organization and related to external environment. Strategy in business literature is a relatively newer term and is still evolving. In the 1960s the focus was on long range planning, in 1970s on portfolio approach, in 1980s on competitive strategy and in 1990s on core competencies and resource based view of the firm. During the year 2000 to 2010 a type of monopoly strategy called blue ocean strategy is discussed a lot and after 2010, due to enhanced focus on sustainable environment, green ocean strategy got importance. During the last century, before globalization, the focus of business strategy has been primarily used by the organizations belonging to the developed countries like USA, Western Europe and Japan. Since USA had taken a lead in business education after industrialization, the concept of strategy has found its origin in business context primarily in the USA (Pillania, 2009) [1]. There are various emerging concepts in strategy at corporate level, business level and functional level including marketing strategy, human resource strategy, financial strategy and operations strategy etc. In this paper, we have identified various modern strategies used by organizations as their business strategies and correlated their base in Indian epics by narrating the instances of various strategic models used in Indian philosophy of Vedanta, Upanishad, Ramayana, Mahabharata and other moral stories. The strategies used in Indian epics as examples for various modern strategies are also analysed using PEST framework and ABCD framework.

2. STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT : A TOOL FOR WINNERS

Strategy is the direction and scope of an organization over the long term. Ideally the strategy matches its resources to its changing environment and in particular, its markets, customers or clients, so as to meet stakeholder's expectations so that it ensures achieving the objectives of the organization. Strategy is used by managers of business organizations at 3 main levels of corporate, business, and functional [2].

Corporate Strategy : At the highest or corporate level the strategy provides long range guidance for the whole organizations as – What business or businesses the firm should be in ? It relates the future formula and structure of the company and the business in which it intends to compete. The overachieving strategy of a company developed by its leadership that reflects its mission and core values in its goals and underlying business strategies for achieving them. The corporate strategy provides clear direction for all the business units working in coordination to meet shareholder expectations while providing value to their customers and employees [3].

Business Level Strategy : Here the concern is with the products and services that should be offered in the market defined at the corporate level – How do we compete in this business ? Business Level strategy is also sometimes called competitive strategy. The term that is often used in relation to business strategy is Strategic Business Unit

(SBU). SBU means a unit within the overall corporate entity for which there is an external market for its goods and services which is distinct from that of another SBU. A business strategy is the means by which it sets out to achieve its desired ends (objectives). It can simply be described as a long-term business planning. Typically a business strategy will cover a period of about 3-5 years (sometimes even longer). A business strategy is concerned with major resource issues e.g. raising the finance to build a new factory or plant. Strategies are also concerned with deciding on what products to allocate major resources to [4]. Strategies are concerned with the scope of a business' activities i.e. what and where they produce.

Two main categories of strategies can be identified:

1. Generic (general) strategies, and
2. Competitive strategies.

The main types of generic strategies that organisations can pursue are:

1. Growth i.e. the expansion of the company to purchase new assets, including new businesses, and to develop new products.
2. Internationalisation/globalisation i.e. moving operations into more and more countries.
3. Retrenchment involves cutting back to focus on your best lines. The Americans refer to this as 'sticking to the knitting' - i.e. concentrating on what you do best.

Functional level Strategy : The functions of the business (e.g. operations, marketing, finance) make long-range plans which support the competitive advantage being pursued by the business strategy, - How does the function contribute to the corporate and business strategy ? This is also called operational Strategy [5].

3. STRATEGIC MODELS AT BUSINESS LEVEL

Corporate strategy is defined as the positioning and relating of the firm/organisation to its environment in a way which will assure its continued success and make it sure from surprises (Ansoff H. I. 1987) [6]. Several factors decide corporate strategy to emerge successful such for instance is growth, stability, profitability and efficiency. Growth involves the expansion of a business, its markets, products, services, size etc. Successful growth strategies are based on having the resources to support growth, identifying the markets that make growth worthwhile being better in competition in these growth markets. Stability involves a consolidation strategy for the organisation, often before a period of growth. The organisation needs to establish clear procedures and systems during this period before moving on. Seeking profit is an important business strategy, particularly in organisations where shareholders have considerable influence. Efficiency is concerned with how well resources have been used in meeting organisational objectives. It is important for public sector service organisations to show that taxpayers funds have been used well. This apart, market leadership strategies aims to grab the global market. The market leader is able to gain considerable cost advantages over rivals because by definition other firms will have a smaller market share and therefore fewer opportunities for economies of scale. Beyond all these, survival is essential in a highly competitive business environment. Survival is the key to most organisations. Only by surviving they are able to develop other strategies. Apart from above, strategies of an organization or individual are divided into another class as (1) competitive strategies also called Red ocean strategies (Porter M.E. 1998) [7], (2) monopoly strategy called Blue ocean strategy (Han Kim W. 2006) [8], (3) sustainable strategy called Green ocean strategy (Hou, Shengtian, 2007) [9], (4) a mix of Blue and Green called Purple ocean strategy (Babelfish, 2007)[10], (5) unethical strategy for one time survival called black ocean strategy (Aithal P.S 2015) [11] and combined/white ocean strategies used in this paper.

Think of the market as an ocean and the competing organizations as sharks fighting each other and striving to prevail. The bloodshed makes the ocean turn red. That is why the competing strategies followed by the organizations are called red ocean strategies (Porter M. E. 1980) [12]. Red oceans represent all the industries in existence today in the known market space. In red oceans, industry boundaries are defined and accepted, and the competitive rules of the game are well understood. Here, companies try to outperform their rivals in order to grab a greater share of existing demand. As the space gets more and more crowded, prospects for profits and growth are reduced. Products turn into commodities, and increasing competition turns the water bloody. Red ocean strategy supports to compete in existing market space, beat the competition, exploit existing demand, make the value/cost trade-off, align the whole system of a company's activities with its strategic choice of differentiation or low cost (Porter M. E. 1980) [12].

Blue oceans denote all the industries not in existence today- the unknown market space, untainted by competition. In blue oceans, demand is created rather than fought over. There is ample opportunity for growth that is both profitable and rapid. There are two ways to create blue oceans. In a few cases, companies can give rise to completely new industries, as eBay did with the online auction industry. But in most cases, a blue ocean is created from within a red ocean when a company alters the boundaries of an existing industry. Blue ocean strategy supports to create uncontested market space, make the competition irrelevant, create and capture new demand, break the value/cost trade-

off, align the whole system of a company's activities in pursuit of differentiation and low cost (Kim W. C., and Mauborgne R. 2004) [13].

Green Ocean Strategy is a recent strategic outcome with two different types of schools of thought. According to first school of thought, it is a strategy to gauge the impact of environmental footprint on human lives. From different unstructured documents like newspapers, magazines, world wide web pages, it is revealed that automobile industry happens to be one of the largest contributors of environmental pollution throughout the world. India, as an emerging economy, has become a lucrative market destination for automobiles. Due to high level of global competition, a plethora of global automobile players have crowded in this second largest market. This phenomenon coupled with influx of other industries has blown up the environmental footprint in India leaving an adverse impact on human lives [8]. According to second school of thought, it is a hybrid mechanism which combines the best things that characterize Blue ocean and Red ocean strategies. The keyword in discussing this theory is *sustainability* and there can be no one-size-fits-all formula governing the innovation mechanism of an organization [14-15]. Based on organizational analysis, it is observed that some of the organizations and individuals especially in developing countries use a new type of strategy for survival and sustainability at least for short term to overcome their intensive problem and to get quick relief from the problems. Such a strategy and named it as "Black Ocean Strategy" [16]. Black ocean strategy is a kind of survival strategy to foresee the organizational problems and solve them successfully to continue in its business market by means of a kind of black magic may be legally or illegally, ethically or unethically. Based on our observation and focus group study we have developed this concept systematically and studied the conditions and characteristics of this model of decision-making called Black ocean strategy. Various Strategies used in Modern Business Management are listed in table 1. These strategies if implemented properly, ensure organizational success either for short term or for long term.

Table 1 : Details of various strategic models used in business management :

S. No.	Type of Strategy	Details
1	Red Ocean Strategy	Red ocean strategy supports to compete in existing market space, beat the competition, exploit existing demand, make the value/cost trade-off, align the whole system of a company's activities with its strategic choice of differentiation or low cost.
2	Blue Ocean Strategy	Blue ocean strategy supports to create uncontested market space, make the competition irrelevant, create and capture new demand, break the value/cost trade-off, align the whole system of a company's activities in pursuit of differentiation and low cost.
3	Green Ocean Strategy	Green ocean strategy to support the impact of environmental footprint on human lives. From different unstructured documents like newspapers, magazines, world wide web pages, it is revealed that automobile industry happens to be one of the largest contributors of environmental pollution throughout the world and hence it has to incorporate green ocean strategy.
4	Purple Ocean Strategy	A mix of Blue ocean and Green ocean strategy is called Purple ocean strategy.
5	Black Ocean Strategy	Black ocean strategy is a kind of survival strategy to foresee the organizational problems and solve them successfully to continue in its business market by means of a kind of black magic may be legally or illegally, ethically or unethically.
6	White Ocean Strategy (WOS) (DanaiChanchaochai's Model)	White Ocean's concept is concerning about "social" more than "profit" that made WOS outstanding than the others oceans which is gaining reputation and profit from their customer by using any strategies to be apart or win the competition in market. The concept of WOS is focusing on People, Planet, Profit and Passion. Concern for society and environment is most important in this ocean. Both WOS and Green ocean strategies have same objective of preserving environment and hence society.
7	White Ocean Mixed Strategy	Mixture of red ocean, blue ocean, green ocean and black ocean strategies for organisational survival, sustainability and profit.
8	Ideal strategy	A planning and execution strategy which conforms the success of the work in any situational conditions and constraints. This strategy ensures the sustainability of the organization with huge profit.

4. Indian Philosophy & Epics :

The Indian philosophy is believed to be started from Vedic period. The ancient Rishis, settled in the forests, meditated over the fundamental questions of existence of life, its creation, its constituents, its creator with an intension to know the nature of reality. Indian philosophy distinctly exhibits a spiritual bent and supported the development of religion as well with philosophy. Indian philosophy takes a comprehensive view of metaphysics, epistemology, psychology, ethics etc., instead of separately dealt like in western philosophy and had positive influence on the life of masses. Indian

philosophy describes four basic goals (*purusharthas*) of life. They are *artha*, *kama*, *dharma* and *moksha*. Based on changes in nature of growth, Indian philosophy is divided into four main periods. The first period called the Vedic Period placed between 2500 and 600 B.C.E. This is the age of the assimilation and culmination of the great Vedas, Aranyakas and Upanishads which have influenced Indian thought process since then [17].

During the second period called the Epic Period, placed between 600 B.C.E. to 200 C.E. the great epics of Mahabharata and Ramayana were written and the early development of Buddhism, Jainism, Shaivism and Vaishnavism took place simultaneously. Bhagavad-Gita, which is a part of Mahabharata considered as one of the three most authoritative texts of Indian philosophical literature. The philosophies of skepticism, naturalism and materialism started and the orthodox systems of Hinduism got their shape. In addition, social and ethical philosophies along with the codes of conduct were compiled in the form called Dharmashastras [18]. The philosophical thought and discussions had their origins during this Epic Period.

During the third period called the Sutra Period, dated approximately the early centuries of the Christian era, short enigmatic aphorisms named Sutras were written as treatises to the earlier schools of philosophical thoughts, in systematic and orderly forms.

During the fourth period which lasts from the Sutra Period to the 17th century, called the Scholastic Period, commentaries on sutras were written and further commentaries on commentaries were also written by many philosophers, including Shankaracharya, Sridhara, Ramanujacharya, Madhvacharya, Vachaspati, Kumarlila, Udayana, Bhaskara, Jayanta, Vijnabhikshu and Raghunatha. Along with commenting on the ancient systems, some of these philosophers have developed their own systems like Shankaracharya's Advaita, Ramanujacharya's Vihsishtadvaita and Madhvacharya's Dvaita systems [18].

5. STRATEGY MODELS & INDIAN EPICS

When we study Indian epics, there are many instances where the modern strategic management models are used to face and solve problems. In this paper, we have narrated the instances of various strategic models used in the great epics of Mahabharata, Ramayana, and Bhagavad-Gita and co-related them to various strategic models mentioned in the table 2.

Table 2 : Examples of various strategies used in Indian Epics

S. No.	Business Strategy	Example in Indian Epics
1	Red Ocean strategy	(1) In Ramayana, the competition between Wali and Sugriva to gain the Vanara kingdom. (2) In Ramayana, the competition between Kaikeyee and Kausalya to establish their sons as king. (3) In Mahabharata, the competition between Pandava and Kaurava. (4) The war between Karna and Arjuna in Mahabharata (5) The fight between Drona and Arjuna during Mahabharata war. (6) The war between Bheema and Duryodhana during Mahabharata war.
2	Blue Ocean Strategy	(1) The strategy of Hanuman to get friendship of Srirama. (2) The unique ability of Ravana to use Aeroplane called Pushpaka Vimana. (3) Ashwamedha Yagha of Pandava's after Mahabharath war. (4) The uniqueness of Bhishmacharya's capability of winning and deciding on his own death (5) The uniqueness of Hanuma to jump to Himalaya or to Lanka. (6) The uniqueness of Sri Rama in divorcing Sitha based on comment by his citizen. (7) The uniqueness of Dharmaraja in maintaining truthfulness in Mahabharata story.
3	Green Ocean Strategy	(1) Srirama's exile for 14 years and the way lived in the forest. (2) Pandava's exile for 12 years which included one year of

		<p>‘Ajnathavasa’ (living in disguise).</p> <p>(3) The mediation of compromise between Rama and Ravana in Ramayana by Hanuman.</p> <p>(4) The war between Vali and Sugreeva to solve their misunderstandings.</p> <p>(5) The war between Bheema and Jarasandha without using other forces.</p>
4	Black Ocean Strategy	<p>(1) In Ramayana the strategy of Kaikeyee, the wife of King Dasharatha to send Lord Srirama to Forest.</p> <p>(2) In Ramayana the sister of Ravana, named Shurpanakha tried to marry Srirama through this strategy but failed.</p> <p>(3) In Ramayana the King of Lanka – Ravana also followed this strategy to hijack Sitha, the wife of Srirama.</p> <p>(4) In Ramayana, the hero of the story, Srirama also followed this strategy to kill Wali, the king of Vanaras.</p> <p>(5) In Mahabharata, Srikrishna, the disguise of God, followed this strategy to kill Karna, the king of Vanga.</p> <p>(6) In Mahabharata, the Kauravas followed this strategy to kill Abhimanyu, the son of Arjuna in Chakravyuha.</p> <p>(7) In Mahabharata, Shakuni, the uncle of Kauravas, followed this strategy to win the game of dice in favour of Kauravas against Pandavas.</p> <p>(8) In Mahabharata, the elder brother of Pandavas, named Dharmaraja followed this strategy to fool his teacher, named Dronacharya and subsequent killing by Arjuna.</p> <p>(9) In Mahabharata, Bhima, the middle brother of Pandavas has followed this strategy to kill Duryodhana.</p> <p>(10) In Ramayana, the strategy of Maricha, in the form of disguised deer to attract Sita.</p>
5	White Ocean Mixed Strategy	<p>(1) In Ramayana, the strategy used by Srirama to get back his wife Sita.</p> <p>(2) In Ramayana, the strategy used by Hanuman to become special servant and devotee of Srirama.</p> <p>(3) In Ramayana, the strategy used by Sugreeva the king of Vanaras to gain King position with the help of Lord Srirama.</p> <p>(4) In Ramayana, the strategy used by Vibhishana the brother of King Ravana, to gain the kingship of Lanka.</p> <p>(5) In Mahabharata, the strategy used by Arjuna to see that he is winner in all wars with the help of Lord Srikrishna.</p> <p>(6) In Mahabharata, the strategy used by Lord Srikrishna is also mixed strategy.</p> <p>(7) In Mahabharata, the strategy used by Draupadi, the wife of Pandavas is a white ocean mixed strategy.</p> <p>(8) In Mahabharata, the strategy used by Bhima is also white ocean mixed strategy.</p> <p>(9) In Panchatantra stories, many instances are depicted on mixed strategies.</p>
6	Other Strategies	<p>(1) In Mahabharata many other strategies like <i>team performance strategies</i> used by Pandavas as well as Kauravas is depicted.</p> <p>(2) In Ramayana also the <i>team performance strategy</i> is used by Lord Srirama, Lakshmana, Hanuman and military of Vanaras.</p> <p>(3) <i>Collaborative strategy</i> is used both in Ramayana and Mahabharata.</p>

6. STRATEGY INSTANCES AND IMPLEMENTATION IN INDIAN EPICS

(1) Instances of Red ocean strategy :

(i) In Ramayana, the competition between the king Wali and his brother Sugriva to gain the power of Vanara kingdom Kishkinda is a classic example of Red ocean strategy. The fight between younger brother Sugriva and elder brother Wali is continuously intensified and finally the younger brother took the help of Lord Srirama to solve his problem of liberating his wife from the custody of his elder brother Wali.

(ii) In Ramayana, the competition between Kaikeyee and Kausalya, the wives of Dasharatha the king of Ayodhya, in order to get the kingship position to their children Bharatha and Srirama respectively is another example of Red ocean strategy. The entire story of Ramayana is the consequence of this competition strategy.

(iii) In Mahabharata, the competition between Pandavas and Kauravas in order to get power to become the permanent ruler of Hasthinapura. The entire war at Kurukshetra has happened for this purpose. To win in the competition, Pandavas used the help of Lord Srikrishna and Kauravas used the power of their team members.

(iv) The war between Karna and Arjuna in Mahabharata is also an example of competitive strategy between Kauravas and Pandavas.

(v) The fight between Drona and Arjuna, the teacher and the student during Mahabharath war even if they had mutual respect to each other.

(vi) The war between Bheema and Duryodhana during Mahabharath war is also to get the ruling power on Hasthinapur.

Similarly there are many incidents and instances in both Ramayana and Mahabharata epics on implementation of competitive or red ocean strategy.

(2) Instances of Blue ocean strategy :

(i) The strategy used by Hanuman to get friendship of Srirama by his unique way of serving Rama and showing his gratitude towards his god Srirama.

(ii) The unique ability of Ravana to use Aeroplane called Pushpaka Vimana to hijack Sitamatha to Lanka is a unique technology implementation strategy to fly in air.

(iii) Ashwamedha Yaga of Pandavas after Mahabharata war is a unique way at that time to show their power and expansion of kingdom. Ashwamedha Yaga is the symbol of creating uncontested empire.

(iv) The uniqueness of Bhishmacharya's capability of winning and deciding on his own death is the monopoly strategy in deciding even his death. Bhishma the grand teacher of both Pandavas and Kauravas has uncontested capability of even controlling his own death.

(v) The uniqueness of Hanuman to jump to Himalaya or to Lanka using his uncontested power as well as uncontested devotion towards his lord Srirama.

(vi) The uniqueness of Sri Rama in divorcing Sitha based on comment by his citizen in his principle of giving justice and confidence to each and every citizen of his empire equally.

(vii) The uniqueness of Dharmaraja, the eldest brother of Pandavas in maintaining truthfulness in Mahabharath story at all instances in his life.

(viii) The uniqueness of Karna, unofficial brother of Pandavas in his sacrifice to his Master Duryodhana until he end his life.

Similarly there are many incidents and instances one can see in both Ramayana and Mahabharath epics on implementation of monopoly or blue ocean strategy.

(3) Instances of Green ocean strategy :

(i) Pandavas spent twelve year in exile with the poor people and the years of exile helped them to reach out to people from various strata of the society while Kaurava's had no experience of the ground reality as they lived a royal life. Managers need to understand the realities to lead their team in the right direction. They need to break the barriers to get in touch with their subordinates to understand their problems and identify ways to make their work easier.

(ii) Srirama's exile for 14 years of living in forest and the way he lived in the forest. This shows the view and perception of Lord Srirama in finding peace and living in unpolluted good environment. This also teaches today's generation to maintain clean and green environment to maintain good health.

(iii) Pandava's living in disguise for one year during their period of twelve years exile shows their energy to face challenges.

(iv) The mediation of compromise between Rama and Ravana in Ramayana by Hanuman to solve the problem of releasing Sitamatha is also an effort to avoid war and death of innocents in the process of maintaining good physical and mental health of the people.

(v) The sole fight between Wali and Sugreeva to resolve their mis-understandings at Kishkinda without using massive weapons and army to avoid environmental damage is also an example of implementation of green ocean strategy in Ramayana epic.

(vi) The sole fighting between Bheema and Jarasandha in Ramayana epic, without using army and weapons is also a classic example of their perception and responsibility of maintaining green environment for future generations.

(4) Instances of Black ocean strategy :

- (i) In Ramayana the strategy of Kaikeyee, the wife of King Dasharatha to send Srirama to forest by means of influencing and cheating her own husband King Dasharatha.
- (ii) In Ramayana the sister of Ravana, named Shurpanakha has tried to marry Srirama through this strategy but failed.
- (iii) In Ramayana the King of Lanka – Ravana also followed Black ocean strategy to hijack Sithamatha, the wife of Lord Srirama.
- (iv) In Ramayana, the hero of the story, Lord Srirama also followed this strategy to kill Wali, the king of Vanaras. This is the only black spot in his clean image throughout the story.
- (v) In Mahabharata, Srikrishna, the disguise of God, followed this strategy to kill Karna, the king of Vanga through Arjuna. Lord Krishna met Karna in the disguise of a poor begger and fooled him by asking his life protecting jacket as charity.
- (vi) In Mahabharata, the Kauravas followed this strategy to kill Abhimanyu, the son of Arjuna in Chakravyuha.
- (vii) In Mahabharata, Shakuni, the uncle of Kauravas, followed this strategy of cheating to win the game of dice in favour of Kauravas against Pandavas and made them to go to forest for 12 years.
- (viii) In Mahabharata, the elder brother of Pandavas, named Dharmaraja has followed this strategy to fool his teacher, named Dhronacharya and subsequently killing him by Arjuna. For this purpose, Lord Krishna made truthfull person Dharmaraja to utter false information to Dhronacharya and made him to believe.
- (ix) In Mahabharata, Bhima, the middle brother of Pandavas has followed this strategy to kill Duryodhana of Kauravas by hitting him at below the waist which is illegal as per law.
- (x) In Ramayana, the strategy of Maricha, the uncle of Ravana in the form of disguised deer to attract SitaMatha is also a form of black ocean strategy.

(5) Instances of White ocean mixed strategy :

- (i) Krishna has acted as a greatest crisis manager showing how to take calculated risks at the time of crisis. Management is all about taking calculated risks. Shying away from challenges is not a sign of management, rather well-assessed decisions to on facing the challenges is the trademark of good management.
- (ii) In Ramayana, the strategy used by Srirama to get back his wife Sitamatha by means of various strategies to ensure win is White ocean mixed strategy.
- (iii) In Ramayana, the strategy used by Hanuman to become special servant and devotee of Lord Srirama and ensured win in his objective of gaining Srirama's friendship, love and affection is also an example of White ocean mixed strategy.
- (iv) In Ramayana, the strategy used by Sugreiva the king of Vanaras to gain King position with the help of Lord Srirama by following different strategies at different times and finally to ensure winning is also an example for White ocean mixed strategy.
- (v) In Ramayana, the strategy used by Vibhishana, the brother of King Ravana, to gain the kingship of Lanka with the help of Lord Srirama is also an example of mixed strategy.
- (vi) In Mahabharata, the strategy used by Arjuna to see that he is winner in all wars with the help of Lord Srikrishna is also an example of White ocean mixed strategy.
- (vii) In Mahabharath, the strategy used by Lord Srikrishna in the process of helping good people (Pandavas) and affecting bad people (Kauravas) is also mixed strategy.
- (viii) In Mahabharath, the strategy used by Draupadi, the wife of Pandavas to ensure winning in all challenges is also a survival mixed strategy.
- (ix) In Mahabharath, the strategy used by Bhima to face challenges is also white ocean mixed strategy.
- (x) In Panchatantra stories, many instances are depicted on mixed strategies.

7. ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIES

A business strategy is a long term plan developed systematically to achieve the objectives of the organization. Usually it covers a period of 3-5 years or longer and deals major resource issues of the organization including raising the finance to build a new factory or plant, expansion of business geographically, collaborations with competitors, going for new products or services, implementing new technology etc.

As per old school of thought, the two main categories of strategies are identified as Generic strategies, and Competitive strategies.

Generic strategies include : (1) Growth strategy, which include the expansion of the organization to purchase new assets, including new businesses, and to develop new products. (2) Internationalisation/globalisation Strategy, which include moving operations into other countries.

(3) Retrenchment strategy, which involves cutting back to focus on core activities by outsourcing other activities in which the organization has no core competency.

Competitive strategies are related to doing things better than rivals. To be competitive a firm shouldn't just copy the ideas of rivals. They should seek to out compete rivals. There are two main ways of being competitive.

(1) Low Cost Strategy : By selling goods at lower prices than rivals, the company can be the market leader and get benefits from economies of scale.

(2) Differentiation Strategy : By differentiating the products or services from those of rivals, a firm can charge a higher price called premier price if desired.

(3) Economies of Scale: By producing large volumes of output products, big firms have advantages to spread their variable costs over large units of output.

As per new school of thought, the six main categories of strategies are given in table 1, which include Red ocean strategy, Blue ocean strategy, Green ocean strategy, Black ocean strategy, and White ocean mixed strategy. The instances of these strategies used in the Indian epics are identified in table 2.

Red ocean strategy is the new name of competitive strategy used to beat the competitors by overtaking them in terms of the business performance. The entire Mahabharata epic is developed based on this strategy. The entire story is about the competition between Pandavas and Kauravas to catch the empire. Similarly, the entire epic Ramayana is developed with the competition between Srirama and Ravana to retain or capture Sithadevi respectively.

Blue ocean strategies are also used in Mahabharata as well as Ramayana as monopoly strategies.

Green ocean strategies are used both in Mahabharata as well as Ramayana as environmental sustainability strategy by keeping the king Rama and the Pandavas in forest for 14 years and 12 years respectively.

Black ocean strategies are also used extensively in both Ramayana and Mahabharata in form of strategies used by Duryodhana, the king of Kauravas, Shakuni, the uncle of Kauravas, Kamsa, the King of Mathura, Yudisthira, the king of Pandavas, at different instances of the story. Similarly in the Ramayana, Manthara, the anti of Srirama, Shurpanakha, the sister of Ravana, and Srirama in front of Wali have used black ocean strategies along with many other instances.

White ocean mixed strategies is considered as optimum strategy and is the intelligent mix of other strategies based on environmental, economic, political, social and technological situations which affecting the performance of the business organization.

Developing White ocean mixed strategy as a global strategy

After globalization, the economy of the countries became interdependent and the time taken for people to travel between continents has been significantly reduced due to advents in transportation technology. The penetration of internet and telecommunication connects the people worldwide instantaneously. The business response of large multinational business organisations has to recognise that they are now operating in a global market place and have to develop appropriate strategies. A global strategy is an organisational plan that takes into account these new global realities. The white ocean mixed strategies is considered as optimum strategy and is going to be global strategy in future days due to its relevance international and multinational business problems which are occurring due to environmental, economic, political, social and technological reasons affecting the performance of the business organization. When we go through the great epics of Mahabharata and Ramayana, we can understand that the two parties in Mahabharata the Pandavas and Kauravas, and in Ramayana, the Srirama and Ravana have used White ocean mixed strategy as optimum strategy because all other strategies are used wherever required.

PEST Analysis

Creating a global strategy based on White ocean strategy products/services involves first carrying out an environmental analysis of political, economic, social, and technological trends that are relevant to the products or services operating on a global scale. Having a clear set of objectives about product/services strategic plans has to be developed which enables the organisation to focus on global markets. A key element of this global strategy will be a global marketing plan identifying an appropriate marketing mix, coupled with production and distribution plans of the product/service. The PEST analysis of the organization include [21] Political Environment analysis, Economic Environment analysis, Social Environment analysis, and Technological Environment analysis. Based on PEST analysis of organizational global strategy can be co-related with White ocean mixed strategy as optimum strategy, an organization can be sustainable in global business.

8. CONCLUSION

Our study on various modern strategies used in Indian epics, we found that both in R & M, the RS, BS, GS, and BS are used at appropriate times in order to ensure winning in a given challenge. Both the epics have used an optimum mix of the above strategies so that the new strategic model called White ocean mixed strategy is generally applicable. We have also discussed the global strategy of the organizations should be the optimum mixture of all the strategies

and is to be called as White ocean mixed strategy. This is according to the lessons learned in great Indian epics where the winners Pandavas in Mahabharata and Lord Srirama in Ramayana have used optimum mix of all modern strategies i.e., Red ocean, Blue ocean, Green ocean, and even Black ocean at appropriate time.

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